

Anaesthetic Management of a Case with Severe Mitral Stenosis Posted for Emergency Caesarean Section

Dr. Syed Azhar Irfan
Kurnool Medical College
Kurnool, India

Dr. Shaik Mohammed Ghiyazuddin
Kurnool Medical College
Kurnool, India

Abstract:- Mitral stenosis (MS) is the most common valvular heart disease associated with pregnancy. The management of the disease needs to be individualized and requires multidisciplinary care from the time of diagnosis of the disease. We, hereby, present a successful anesthetic management of a patient with severe MS posted for emergency caesarean section

Keywords:- Mitral Stenosis; Caesarean Section.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mitral stenosis is a valvular heart disease. Though its incidence has declined in developed countries, it is a significant problem in tropical and Asian countries. Severe mitral stenosis carries a significant risk for both cardiac and non cardiac surgeries. Hereby, we discuss a case of a patient with severe mitral stenosis posted for emergency caesarean section.

II. CASE REPORT

A 27 year old G4P2L2A1 with 39weeks of gestational age was posted for emergency caesarean section. The patient gave history of breathlessness and palpitations since 3 months with acute exacerbation of symptoms since 3 days. 2D echo was suggestive of RHD with moderate to severe MS (MVA=0.91cm²) with moderate TR and MR along with moderate to severe PAH, global hypokinesia of LV and an EF of 46 - 48%. ECG revealed sinus tachycardia along with P Mitrale. After taking written high risk consent, the patient was taken on OT table and ASA standard monitors were attached. Premedication given with inj Fentanyl 60 micrograms IV, Inj Dexamethasone 8 mg IV, Inj Paracetamol 1g IV infusion and Inj Esmolol 15 mg IV. Induction was done with Inj Etomidate 12 mg IV. Inj Succinylcholine 75mg IV was given and patient was intubated with ET tube of size 7.0mm. Anaesthesia was maintained with O₂ @ 5L/min, Sevoflurane, Inj Atracurium 15+5+5 mg IV and Inj Fentanyl 40 µg IV. Inj Esmolol 5 mg IV was given at regular intervals to control tachycardia. After delivery of the baby, 10 IU of Oxytocin was given via IV infusion and Inj Furosemide 40 mg IV. Total fluid input was

300 ml and she had an output of 250 ml. She was extubated after giving Inj Neostigmine 2.5mg and Inj Glycopyrrolate 0.4 mg IV. She maintained SPO₂ of 99% on room air and was shifted to recovery room and kept on Oxygen supplementation post operatively @ 6L/min. Post op vitals: PR=89/min, BP=120/74 mm hg and SPO₂=100% . The patient was shifted to ICU for next 3 days and post op analgesia was maintained with Inj Paracetamol and Inj Fentanyl SOS. There were no further post op complications and was shifted to ward later.

III. DISCUSSION

The goals for the anaesthetic management of patients with mitral stenosis are maintenance of an acceptable slow heart rate, immediate treatment of acute atrial fibrillation and reversion to sinus rhythm, avoidance of aortocaval compression, maintenance of adequate venous return, maintenance of adequate SVR and prevention of pain, hypoxemia, hypercarbia and acidosis, which may increase pulmonary vascular resistance. Regional anaesthesia has proved to be a safe technique in cardiac patients presenting for caesarean section. Epidural and continuous spinal anaesthetic techniques are attractive options. One of the major advantages of epidural analgesia is that it can be administered in incremental doses and that the total dose could be titrated to the desired sensory level. This allows the maternal cardiovascular system to compensate for the occurrence of sympathetic blockade, resulting in a lower risk of hypotension and decreased utero placental perfusion. General anaesthesia has the disadvantage of increased blood pressure and tachycardia during laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation. A beta adrenergic receptor antagonist and an adequate dose of Opioid like Fentanyl should be administered before or during the induction of general anaesthesia. Because Esmolol has a rapid onset and short duration of action, it is a better choice in controlling tachycardia. Tachycardia inducing drugs like Atropine and Ketamine should be totally avoided. Maintenance of anaesthesia can be carried out with Oxygen and Nitrous Oxide 50:50, Isoflurane, Opioids and Vecuronium. With associated severe pulmonary artery hypertension, nitrous oxide can be omitted.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Padmavati S, “Present status of rheumatic fever and rheumatic heart disease in India”, *Indian Heart J* 1995; 47:395-8
- [2]. R Gopalakrishnan, S Shobha, G Sucheta, “ Anaesthetic management of a case of Severe Mitral Stenosis with twin pregnancy for LSCS”, *Bombay Hospital Journal*, July 1996: 3803
- [3]. Hameed A, Akhter MW, Bitar F, Khan SA, Sarma R, Goodwin TM, et al, “Left atrial thrombosis in pregnant women with mitral stenosis and sinus rhythm”, *Am J ObstetGynecol*2005; 193:501-4.
- [4]. Menachem M. Weiner, M.D.; Torsten P. Vahl, M.D.; Ronald A. Kahn, M.D.; Bruno Riou, M.D., Ph.D., “ Cesarean Section Complicated by Rheumatic Mitral Stenosis”, *Anesthesiology* April 2011, Vol. 114, 949–957.